

Network Effects and Creating Global Micro-Communities

Michael Gord^a

^a *Founder & CEO of MLG Blockchain Consulting, Toronto, Ontario, Canada*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

An Airdrop is when a large number of people are able to receive a set number of tokens by attending an event to learn about the token project and community. If these micro-communities are given the resources to grow, what starts as a small group of disjointed enthusiasts can become a powerful thriving distributed global organization.

2. Aim

To introduce the concept of an Airdrop and explain how creating global micro communities can lead to large scale macroeconomic changes.

3. Material and methods

Michael Gord has hosted global airdrops since 2015 at universities and tech hubs around the world. He has learnt how to optimize the airdrop to ensure that the communities around the world learn about the token, understand how to hold it and use it and how to empower the community leaders to continue to grow their community.

4. Results

Michael and his team have airdropped tokens to thousands of people in cities around the world and has launched thriving micro-communities.

5. Conclusions

Airdrops are a great way to generate interest for token projects and create micro-communities which leads to large scale societal change.

6. Keywords

Airdrops are a great way to generate interest for token projects and create micro-communities which leads to large scale societal change.

February 4, 2018

Author biography

Michael Gord Michael Gord is the founder and CEO of MLG Blockchain, an enterprise blockchain and ICO consulting and development firm, and the director of the Blockchain Education Network, a robust global network of blockchain enthusiasts. Michael is also the founder and CEO of Bitcoin Canada, sits on the board of directors of the Blockchain Association of Canada, is an advisor and investor into several prominent blockchain ventures and writes for Bitcoin Magazine in addition to several other fintech publications.

Michael is an active pioneer in the blockchain industry and has organized global annual events which introduce thousands of people around the world each year to their first bits and to the disruptive potential of blockchain technology. Some of these include the Bitcoin Airdrop, Blockchain Education Month, Blockchain Madness, Blockchain Gauntlet, BitCrawls, etc. Michael is also regularly featured as a speaker at fintech industry events and conferences around the world.

Michael holds a degree in Entrepreneurship, Marketing and Information Systems from the Desautels Faculty of Management at McGill University, where he founded the McGill Cryptocurrency Club and co-founded the McGill Students Fintech Association. After graduating, Michael made the first donation of bitcoin to the McGill Alumni Association.